

SEMANTICS OF TERMS IN LEXICOGRAPHICAL PRACTICE

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the analysis of the main principles and ways of semanticization of lexical units in linguistic and bilingual dictionaries. Key approaches to semantics, such as denotative, functional, and contextual aspects, as well as their significance for the accuracy and informativeness of dictionaries, are considered. Particular attention is paid to the role of semantics in the process of conveying meanings and cultural connotations of terms. Examples from linguistic and bilingual dictionaries are analyzed, which allows us to demonstrate the practical implementation of semantics. The work emphasizes the importance of integrating different ways of semantics to improve the quality of bilingual and specialized dictionaries.

Key words: semantics, denotative, connotative, functional meanings, equivalents, linguistic dictionaries, contextual interpretation.

Semanticization requires a deep study not only of the main meaning of the language unit, but also of its contextual, cultural and emotional aspects. This approach fully defines the possibilities of the word and further clarifies its use in speech. This process occupies a central place in lexicography, especially in the creation of bilingual dictionaries, as it is important for dictionary users to explain the manifestations of words in different contexts. However, in linguistic knowledge, the denotative meaning of terms is primarily important, as their function is to express a clear, unified meaning. We inform that scientific or special terms clearly define mutual concepts and must be interpreted in the same way. In this case, emotional connotations, synonymy or homonymy are not correct.

Terms and their main features:

1. Dominance of denotative meaning.

Scientific and special terms should have only primary, subject-oriented denotative meaning. They require accuracy. For example,

"Phoneme" is the smallest unit of language that serves to distinguish the meanings of words and their grammatical parts (D. Seydullaeva, 2018).

"Morpheme" is the smallest semantic unit of a word, a semantic-morphological unit that stands after sound (D. Seydullaeva, 2018).

These concepts always have the same meaning in language learning and do not have a figurative or emotional load.

2. Lack of emotional connotative meaning.

Scientific terms should not reflect emotional or evaluative types. They show objective information. For example,

It is impossible to say that "Phoneme is an invisible unit of language, it shows the hidden ornament of each word" or "Morpheme is a mysterious component, in which the meaning of words and the source of power are hidden," because emotional connotation arises here.

Connotative description can be used as a tradition in artistic painting, but it is not accepted as a scientific basis.

3. Limited synonymous meanings.

In scientific language, only one term should correspond to one concept. Synonymy may make the concept unclear. For example,

"Lexeme" and "unity of speech" are similar concepts, but "lexeme" is more accurate as a scientific term.

4. Lack of homonymous meanings.

There should be no homonymy between terms, as this can confuse concepts. If terms in the same form mean different meanings, a new term is created for each field to avoid their emergence.

The concept of semanticization is of central importance in the field of lexicography and linguistics, and its task is to determine the meaning of words, their contextual use and grammatical features. The Russian-Karakalpak dictionary of bilingual linguistic terms, published in 1992 on the initiative of our linguists D.S. Nasyrov, A. Bekbergenov and A. Jarimbetov, is an important source for the development of scientific and academic work in the Karakalpak language. The main focus of this dictionary is direct translation of the meanings of words and terms from Russian into Karakalpak. In the dictionary, the denotative meanings of words are given in a clear and simple form, which is intended to simplify the translation process for the user.

At the same time, in some cases, explanations of linguistic terms are given. For example, the grammatical or practical aspects are briefly explained, but the possibilities of contextual or functional application are not always indicated. This dictionary, in accordance with the requirements of its time, served as an easy translation guide for users of the Karakalpak language.

The approach to the semanticization of terms in dictionaries has always been one of the main issues of linguistics. O. Akhmanova's "Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" (1966) and "Tilshunoslik terminlari lug`ati" by Sh. Safarov (2023) are important sources in this direction. The process of semanticization in these dictionaries is not limited to explaining the meanings of terms, but also aims to explain their alternatives in different languages and reflect their linguistic application.

The dictionary of O. Akhmanova, which occupies a significant place in Russian linguistics, covers about 7,000 linguistic terms and encompasses all areas of linguistics (phonetics, morphology, syntax, lexicology, linguistic stylistics). The terms are not only explained, but also translated into English and have alternatives in French, German and Spanish. In this case, each dictionary explanation is distinguished by providing examples of the use of the term and a deeper reflection of their scientific concepts. Furthermore, the practical application of terms in the dictionary is broad and is an important source for researchers, students, and researchers.

One of the famous linguists in Uzbek linguistics, "Tilshunoslik terminlari lug`ati" by Sh. Safarov was created for young researchers and students as a modern resource reflecting the development of modern language knowledge. The dictionary explains a wide range of concepts related to language in the Uzbek language, which further increases its practical significance. In it, each term is given a broader definition, and special attention is paid to their

interconnectedness and application. The dictionary also serves to make it easier for researchers to translate scientific texts and work with them.

In conclusion, the display of terms in dictionaries varies depending on their function and audience. Linguistic dictionaries pay attention to scientific accuracy and widely reflect denotative and functional meanings. Bilingual dictionaries are intended for a wider range of users and also include connotative meanings. Such different aspects of terminology show the mutually complementary properties of dictionaries and increase their importance in the general lexicographic process.

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